

CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF HISTORY TEACHERS USING OF INTEGRATED APPROACH

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***Abstract.** Based on the requirements for the level of general knowledge and professional training of history teachers on the basis of a continuous professional development course, this article discusses the preparation of history teachers to teach history on an integrated basis, abandoning the oral method of teaching, using information technology, and teaching students independent work*

***Keywords:** competence development, professional development, integrative, multimedia, interactive methods, modeling, competence.*

INTRODUCTION

Wide use of integrated education in the educational process is a global trend of world development. World science and in the socio-historical development, the interconnectedness of sciences is raised as an urgent issue, and this urgency will turn into a productive force and an important social institution in society.

As one of the main strategies of the new Uzbekistan, it was noted that there is a need to develop the law "On the procedure and principles of teaching social sciences in the continuous education system" and to put it into practice.

In this direction, Sh.Mirziyoev recommended the creation and implementation of the "Strategy for Humanization of the Continuous Education and Training Sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2030"[1].

In modern education, the need to develop 21st century competencies in students is increasingly recognized. One effective way to develop these competencies is to use an integrated or interdisciplinary curriculum.

At the same time, creating an integrated educational environment, raising the moral-ethical and intellectual development of the young generation to a new level in terms of quality, integrating forms of education into the educational process and the introduction of methods is related to the teaching of history.

In this regard, within the framework of the national curriculum, training of competitive personnel in the society by improving the qualifications of pedagogues and developing their competencies is defined as a priority.

ANALYZE THE LITERATURE

Through the system of continuous professional development, the improvement of the qualifications of history teachers and the mechanism of increasing their level of professional competence and improving their professional skills. is based on riding.

Teaching subjects on the basis of the national curriculum at all stages of the continuous education system requires great skill from pedagogues, which in turn encourages the development of creative-research, practical activity experience of teachers and the level of creativity

competence in professional development courses. . In continuous professional development, there is a reason to conduct research on the improvement of the mechanisms of application of interactive educational technologies and strategies to the educational process.

Pedagogical scientists K.Yoldoshev, S.Matchonov, M.Mirkosimova, R.A. Mavlyanova, D.Sharipova, O.Musurmonova, M.Kuronov, B.Abdullaeva, S. Nishonova, U.Mahkamov, E.Turdikulov, R.Safarova, B.Adizov, A.Choriev, Sh. Mardonov, Sh.Shodmonova, O.Davlatov, A.Ismoilov, Q.Shonazarov, R.Yarmatov, paid special attention to revealing the specific aspects of the development of the student's thinking, spiritual-ethical, creative, artistic, innovative thinking.

Necessity of interdisciplinary relations in the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) scientists such as V.F.Odoevsky, K.D.Ushinsky, P.G.Kulagin, O.I.Bakhtina, N.I.Vorzheykina, N.I.Zaporoghes, A.G.Koloskov, A.A.Vagin, Ye.F.Golovkina introduction of interdisciplinary, integrated forms and methods of education in the teaching of history in the research works and manuals of described the importance of communication between disciplines, the ways of its implementation, in their scientific works [2].

In the 50s of the last century. Complex subjects were created to ensure the integrity of some pedagogical knowledge abroad and in our country. Thus, a comprehensive course of "Social Sciences" (including elements of history, law, geography and civic studies) appeared in the USA. There was an attempt to create a comprehensive course "Culture" in Poland. For example, integrated subjects are mainly introduced in the education system of Great Britain, integrated subjects or separate subjects in Korea and Switzerland, integrated subjects in Australia, separate subjects in Japan, Northern Ireland, Wales, Hong Kong and Germany, and culture in Hungary. educational subjects in the field of science, human and nature integrative sciences, separate educational subjects in the Netherlands, in the Institute of History of the Russian Academy of Sciences, in Ireland, all academic subjects are taught in the form of blocks such as Science and Technology. We are taking the first steps in this area.[3]

RESULTS

In the teaching of history sciences, a mechanism for increasing the level of competence and improving the professional skills of teachers through the special electronic platform "Continuous Professional Education" covering the process of lifelong growth of personal professional potential in accordance with individual and community needs is considered. Perspectives of socio-political development, understanding the essence of many phenomena of nature and society, socialization and culturalization of young people determine the future of the country, preservation of national cultural traditions, values and its development has theoretical and methodological significance, making the research of personal and professional growth of civilized youth an urgent task. [4]

In this regard, the improvement of the methods of teaching history, the introduction of distance and other types of professional training, conducted together with the work process, as well as the traditional training of students in the system of continuous professional development, the interaction of educational institutions It is based on the integration of educational types based on equal partnership and ensuring inter-disciplinary, integrated courses and inter-departmental coherence. In the process of professional development courses, history teachers further develop their specific competences in working with tables, diagrams, maps, creating illustrations, and creating multimedia applications in the integrated subject area of teaching history based on the national curriculum.

As a result of the teacher's creative research, the connection between the study of history and life together with the students in the course of the lessons leads to an increase in the level of knowledge of the students.

Only when the teachers conduct continuous research on methodical improvement of the process, the students master the competences related to science.

This means that students:

- to develop independent work skills;
- the development of the world of thought;
- formation of analysis and comparison skills;
- to develop speaking activity;
- makes it possible to apply theoretical knowledge in practice.

DISCUSSION

Establishing a system of continuous professional development of teaching staff, creating the necessary conditions for the continuous growth of their professional skills and qualification level, retraining in accordance with modern requirements and introducing effective mechanisms of regular training to promote the continuous professional training of these employees at a high level there is a need to constantly update teaching methods in keeping with the times, focusing on riding. Taking into account the reform of pre-school and school education in our country and training courses in the study of history, it is appropriate to determine the following goals of history education in the integrated subject of history education:

- Use of visual aids;
- Application of advanced teaching methodology;
- Effective teaching using a computer;
- Acquaintance with achievements of national and world culture;
- Organization of interactive lessons using new pedagogical and innovative methods.

Based on the requirements for the level of general knowledge and professional training of history teachers based on the continuous professional development course, history teachers should teach history on an integrated basis, abandoning the oral teaching method, multimedia applications based on information technologies and teaching independent work are given great importance. Through this, the improvement of innovative methods and technologies for the development of students' thinking outlook is becoming more important.

CONCLUSION

The goal of continuous professional development of history teachers based on an integrated approach is to ensure that the professional and pedagogical skills of history teachers in the subjects they teach are constantly growing, that they use advanced pedagogical and information technologies, as well as interactive teaching. is to provide the basis for regular updating of professional knowledge, qualifications and skills.

In conclusion, it can be said that the establishment of a system of continuous professional development based on the national curriculum creates the necessary conditions for the continuous growth of professional skills and the level of qualifications, training in accordance with modern requirements and integrated effective mechanisms for regular training. on the basis of implementation, it is aimed at providing high-level continuous professional training of history teachers.

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